

Suitability of Yarn Procurement in the Handloom Sector Following the Analytic Hierarchy Process of Multi-Criteria Decision-Making Technique

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Abstract

Effective supply chain management can help handloom manufacturers build strong relationships with suppliers and ensure the timely delivery of raw materials of desired quality. The research mainly studies the raw material, i.e., the yarn supply chain, in the handloom sector. The supply of yarn at a competitive price and quality is an essential requirement for the weavers of the handloom sector in the present fast-changing global markets. The present study establishes a methodology involving the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) as a mathematical tool to evaluate multiple conflicting criteria for selecting the best alternative for sourcing raw materials. AHP is a popular hierarchical structure model for making decisions involving multiple criteria. Although it is an objective methodology for ranking the alternatives, it is based on a subjective judgment of the relative importance of qualitative and quantitative criteria during its pairwise comparison. This research considers reliability, credit facility availability, cost, ease of availability, and the sub-criteria. The subjective rating of multi-criteria in an AHP technique impacts the criteria weight derived from these and, in turn, influences the selection of the best source for yarn procurement.

Keywords: Analytic Hierarchy Process, Handloom, Sensitivity, Supply chain, Yarn

1. Introduction

Supply chains are the organisations and business activities required to design, manufacture, deliver, and use a product or service. Effective supply chain management necessitates coordinating and integrating all activities, from sourcing raw materials to delivering finished products to customers. Supply chain management has become important for organisations seeking to remain competitive in today's market [1-3].

The textile and apparel industries are highly diverse and heterogeneous. These essential industries in developing economies contribute to wealth creation and job opportunities. On the other hand, weaving by hand is an age-old tradition in India, and handloom textiles are a timeless facet that is a valuable component of generational legacy. The handloom sector accounts for almost 15% of total cloth production, and India produces 95% of the world's handwoven fabric [4]. West Bengal's handloom sector contributes significantly to the state's economy and has a long history and tradition. However, the industry has several obstacles, including low productivity, a weak supply chain, escalated yarn prices, bad working conditions, poor inventory management, and inadequate infrastructure.

Multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) has become an extremely significant and valuable tool for tackling challenges in business decision-making [5]. The Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) was developed by Professor Thomas Saaty [6-9] and is one of the frequently discussed methods of decision-making in which factors are arranged hierarchically.

The literature on textile supply chain management mainly focuses on distribution and marketing activities and has been reported in the literature [10, 11]. Several studies have been conducted on the marketing and socio-economic issues, working conditions, and the designer's role in the handloom sector, and it has been found that the supply of yarn and marketing was the major constraint for the handloom industry [12-15]. The managerial issues in handloom production, marketing, procurement, and the challenges encountered have also been reported in the literature [16]. Several systematic literature reviews and case studies on the handloom, handicraft, and apparel industries emphasised different restrictions and the issues affecting the supply chain [17-20]. Researchers also discussed the difficulties encountered by handloom weavers by presenting a comprehensive analysis of the handloom industry's supply chain [21].

Researchers have reported the Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) technique in various fields in textiles [22-25]. The hybrid AHP-TOPSIS method of multi-criteria decision-making was also used to rank the cotton fibres [26]. Various researchers proposed an AHP-based model for raw jute grading [27-28]. The use of handloom cotton fabrics for summer clothing to rank and select the best fabric relative to a specific end-use has also been reported [29].

The literature survey suggests an urgent need to study supply chain management practices in the Indian handloom industry and West Bengal to identify the vulnerability profile of the traditional handloom sectors. The most critical area identified in the supply chain of handloom industries is raw material, i.e., yarn sourcing. With a reliable and consistent supply of high-quality yarn, the handloom sector can meet the market's demands and produce quality products. The Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) may help determine the best option for the handloom weavers to source yarn. This technique considers various factors such as cost, quality, and reliability to evaluate the available options comprehensively. Using this approach, handloom weavers can select the most suitable source for their yarn, ultimately enhancing their productivity and profitability.

The present research aims to investigate and assess the appropriate supply chain business model of the raw material supply chain of the handloom Industry of West Bengal to compare the relative advantages and disadvantages among the options available for raw material sourcing and to assess and pinpoint the most beneficial option through the MCDM technique. Furthermore, to get a more precise conclusion regarding the preferred way of raw material procurement for various handloom products, sensitivity analysis is also performed by raising the relevance of particular deciding variables among evenness of the yarn (quality) - a lower number is preferable, the yarn's strength (quality) - a high value is desirable, count variations in yarn quality - a lower value is preferable, overtwisting/twist liveliness in the yarn (quality) - a lower value is desired, cost - less value is preferable, credit facility availability (cost) - a higher value is desired, waiting time (service) - a lower value is desired and purchasing difficulties (service) - less value is preferred.

2. Methodology

It is essential to identify yarn suppliers to improve the availability and quality of raw materials for handloom weavers. Implementing effective supply chain management practices can help streamline the procurement process and ensure a steady flow of raw materials to support the industry's growth. Most raw material procurement options include NHDC (National Handloom Development Corporation), the local market, Mahajan / Master Weaver, Burrabazar, Kolkata, and Khadi Society. These sources provide a diverse range of options for handloom weavers to procure raw materials based on their specific needs and preferences. In the raw material supply chain, quality, price, and service (ease of availability, limited waiting period) are the determining elements.

2.1 Multi-Criteria Decision-Making

The primary survey was conducted using a structured questionnaire, as shown in Table 1, and data from this survey were collected and analysed using the MCDM technique since numerous and often conflicting factors are involved.

Table 1: Structured questionnaire and survey scale

Sl. No	Questions	Scale
1	Yarn Count (mostly used)	N/A
2	Purchase Point/Place	5-2 >> easy to difficult access
3	Mode of getting yarn	5-2 >> Cost effective to expensive
4	A lead time for getting yarn	5-2 >> earliest to latest
5	Cost of yarn	5-2 >> cheapest to expensive
6	Yarn Quality - Evenness	5-2 >> Even to Uneven
7	Yarn Quality - Strength	5-2 >> strongest to weakest
8	Yarn Quality – Count Variation	5-2 >> low to high
9	Yarn Quality – Over Twist	5-2 >> low to high

2.1.1 Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP)

The Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) is a widely popular MCDM technique. AHP breaks a complicated MCDM problem down into a structure. The last step of AHP is to look at how an $m \times n$ matrix is put together. The relative value of each option in each criterion is used to build the matrix. The first step in solving a problem is to make a decision hierarchy. This is done by putting the overall goal or aim at the top and the possible solutions at the bottom. The criteria and sub-criteria important to the chosen problem are set at the intermediate levels. Next, the pair-wise comparison matrix is made. This is where the AHP determines the critical factors of the problem's goal. The fundamental relational scale for pair-wise comparisons proposed by Saaty (Saaty, 1980) is shown in Table 2.

Table 2: The fundamental relational scale for pair-wise comparisons

Intensity of importance on an absolute scale	Definition	Explanation
1	Equal importance	Two activities contribute equally to the objective.
3	Moderate importance of one over another	Experience and judgment slightly favour one activity over another.
5	Essential or strong importance	Experience and judgment strongly favour one activity over another
7	Very strong importance	An activity is strongly favoured and its dominance is demonstrated in practice.
9	Extreme importance	The evidence favouring one activity over another is of the highest possible order of affirmation.
2,4,6,8	Intermediate values between two adjacent judgments	When compromise is needed.
Reciprocal	If activity p has one of the above numbers assigned to it when compared with activity q, then q has the reciprocal value when compared with p	

The judgments are entered by using the fundamental scale of AHP. In the pair-wise comparison matrix, the entry c_{ij} denotes the comparative importance of i criteria to j Criteria. In the matrix $c_{ij} = 1$ when $i = j$ and $c_{ji} = \frac{1}{c_{ij}}$. The pair-wise

comparison matrix C_1 is shown as:
$$C_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & c_{12} & \dots & c_{1n} \\ c_{21} & 1 & \dots & c_{2n} \\ \dots & \dots & 1 & \dots \\ c_{n1} & c_{n2} & \dots & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

The normalised weight of the i -th criteria (w_i) is determined by calculating the geometric mean of the above matrix's i -th row (GM $_i$) and then normalising the geometric mean of rows. This can be represented as follows:

$$GM_i = \left\{ \prod_{j=1}^n c_{ij} \right\}^{\frac{1}{n}} \text{ and } w_i = \frac{GM_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n GM_i}$$

The principal eigenvector (λ_{\max}) of the above matrix of the original pair-wise comparison matrix (C_1) is calculated. To check the consistency in pair-wise comparison judgment, the consistency index (CI) and consistency ratio (CR) are calculated by the following equations:

$$CI = \frac{\lambda_{\max} - n}{n - 1} \text{ and, } CR = \frac{CI}{RCI},$$

RCI = random consistency index, and its value can be obtained from Table 3. If the value of CR is 0.1 or less, then the judgment is considered consistent and, therefore, acceptable. Otherwise, the decision maker must reconsider the pair-wise comparison matrix entries. The global weights of sub-criteria are calculated by multiplying the relative weight of sub-criteria by the corresponding criterion and the relative weight of the criterion concerning the objective. After obtaining the global weights of each attribute, the priority index is calculated according to the variant of AHP followed. Finally, the ranking of the alternatives is made based on the index obtained.

Table 3: RCI values of different numbers of attributes

M	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
RCI	0	0	0.58	0.90	1.12	1.24	1.32	1.41	1.45

2.2 Sensitivity Analysis

The level of crosstalk between criterion and ranking was assessed in one of the sensitivity analysis approaches, which covers the essential underpinnings of this methodology. This methodology aims to determine the effect of changes in any criterion weights on the overall ranking of alternatives. Furthermore, this research identifies which criteria influence the final ranking more, allowing for better-informed decision-making. The purpose of this technique is to independently determine the effect of each element on the MCDM outputs. Each criterion's weight was changed by 10% (minor change), 20% (medium change), or 30% (significant change) by raising it. This adjustment enabled decision-makers to analyse the overall ranking's sensitivity to changes in specific criteria. When the criterion weights are altered by 10%, 20%, or 30%, the relative sensitivity coefficients illustrate how the rankings of the alternatives vary.

3. Results and Discussions

Raw material supply has been identified as a major bottleneck in West Bengal's handloom industry. Raw materials, like yarns, have a significant impact on both the efficiency of the manufacturing process and the quality of the finished product. In addition, the industry's inability to keep up with market demands and production consistently is hampered by the instability of the supply chain.

Several accessible yarn-sourcing points were identified during the study after discussions with various handloom weavers and stakeholders following an extensive survey. Local yarn suppliers, for example, offer a wide range of options suitable for handloom weaving. Furthermore, some weavers have formed cooperatives to source yarn collectively directly from manufacturers, ensuring fair prices and quality control. During the survey, it was noticed that the handloom weavers mainly prefer to procure yarns from NHDC (National Handloom Development Corporation), Burrabazar, Kolkata, local market, Mahajan (agent), and Khadi society. The quality, price, timeliness, dependability, and availability of credit are all important areas of the yarn supply chain. Given the potential for competing priorities among these factors, a rigorous mathematical analysis is required to pick the optimal solution. This analysis helps develop a workable solution that satisfies all constraints with as few drawbacks as possible. A reasonable and sensible result can be attained by weighing these factors in a systematic mathematical format. This analysis will help to reach a reasonable conclusion that satisfies all needs while keeping costs to a minimum. Allocation of resources, time constraints, and risk assessment are just some of the considerations in the structured mathematical analysis. Decision-makers can maximise the desired outcome by making well-informed choices after carefully considering these factors. This method is also helpful in spotting potential compromises and striking a fair balance between competing goals.

Since most respondents need more resources to pursue higher levels of education, it was unrealistic to anticipate a detailed response (either technically or monetarily). Therefore, the study specified subjective responses on a scale. This subjective structure promotes a wider variety of opinions, ensuring that the wants and needs of a larger number of people are met. Decision-makers gain valuable insights into respondents' general attitudes and preferences through a scaling method, which collects quantitative data that can be analysed and compared. Decisions made using this method are ultimately more well-informed and thorough. Tables 4 - 8 depict the questionnaire and answers in the survey scale method for the yarn purchased from NHDC, Burrabazar, Kolkata, local market, Mahajan, and Khadi society, respectively. Figure 1 discusses the hierarchical structure of the value of the marketing chain.

Table 4: Questionnaire and answers in the survey scale method for the yarn purchased from NHDC

Sl. No	Questions	Scale	Modal value
1	Yarn Count (mostly used)	N/A	
2	Purchase Point/Place	5-2 >> easy to difficult access	5
3	Mode of getting yarn	5-2 >> Cost effective to expensive	5
4	A lead time for getting yarn	5-2 >> earliest to latest	4
5	Cost of yarn	5-2 >> cheapest to expensive	5
6	Yarn Quality - Evenness	5-2>> Even to Uneven	3
7	Yarn Quality - Strength	5-2 >> strongest to weakest	4
8	Yarn Quality – Count Variation	5-2 >> low to high	3
9	Yarn Quality – Over Twist	5-2 >> low to high	5

Table 5: Questionnaire and answers in survey scale method for the yarn purchased from Burrabazar, Kolkata

Sl. No	Questions	Scale	Modal value
1	Yarn Count (mostly used)	N/A	
2	Purchase Point/Place	5-2 >> easy to difficult access	5
3	Mode of getting yarn	5-2 >> Cost effective to expensive	5
4	A lead time for getting yarn	5-2 >> earliest to latest	3
5	Cost of yarn	5-2 >> cheapest to expensive	2
6	Yarn Quality - Evenness	5-2>> Even to Uneven	3
7	Yarn Quality - Strength	5-2 >> strongest to weakest	4
8	Yarn Quality – Count Variation	5-2 >> low to high	3
9	Yarn Quality – Over Twist	5-2 >> low to high	5

Table 6: Questionnaire and answers in the survey scale method for the yarn purchased from the local market

Sl. No	Questions	Scale	Modal value
1	Yarn Count (mostly used)	N/A	
2	Purchase Point/Place	5-2 >> easy to difficult access	5
3	Mode of getting yarn	5-2 >>> Cost effective to expensive	5
4	A lead time for getting yarn	5-2 >> earliest to latest	5
5	Cost of yarn	5-2 >>> cheapest to expensive	2
6	Yarn Quality - Evenness	5-2>>> Even to Uneven	5
7	Yarn Quality - Strength	5-2 >> strongest to weakest	5
8	Yarn Quality – Count Variation	5-2 >> low to high	5
9	Yarn Quality – Over Twist	5-2 >> low to high	5

Table 7: Questionnaire and answers in the survey scale method for the yarn purchased from Mahajan

Sl. No	Questions	Scale	Modal value
1	Yarn Count (mostly used)	N/A	
2	Purchase Point/Place	5-2 >> easy to difficult access	5
3	Mode of getting yarn	5-2 >>> Cost effective to expensive	5
4	A lead time for getting yarn	5-2 >> earliest to latest	5
5	Cost of yarn	5-2 >>> cheapest to expensive	5
6	Yarn Quality - Evenness	5-2>>> Even to Uneven	2
7	Yarn Quality - Strength	5-2 >> strongest to weakest	3
8	Yarn Quality – Count Variation	5-2 >> low to high	2
9	Yarn Quality – Over Twist	5-2 >> low to high	5

Table 8: Questionnaire and answers in the survey scale method for the yarn purchased from the Khadi society

Sl. No	Questions	Scale	Modal value
1	Yarn Count (mostly used)	N/A	
2	Purchase Point/Place	5-2 >> easy to difficult access	5
3	Mode of getting yarn	5-2 >>> Cost effective to expensive	5
4	A lead time for getting yarn	5-2 >> earliest to latest	5
5	Cost of yarn	5-2 >>> cheapest to expensive	2
6	Yarn Quality - Evenness	5-2>>> Even to Uneven	2
7	Yarn Quality - Strength	5-2 >> strongest to weakest	3
8	Yarn Quality – Count Variation	5-2 >> low to high	3
9	Yarn Quality – Over Twist	5-2 >> low to high	5

Figure 1: Hierarchical structure of the value of the marketing chain

Tables 9 – 12 describe a pair-wise comparison matrix of criteria concerning the objective, reliability parameter, ease of availability parameter, and Global weight of criteria and sub-criteria. Beneficial criteria are those where a higher value is desirable, whereas cost criteria are those where a lower value is desirable.

Table 9: Pair-wise comparison matrix of criteria concerning the objective

Criteria	Reliability	Availability of credit facility	Cost	Ease of availability	Geometric Mean (GM)	Normalised GM	Consistency Ratio (CR)
Reliability	1	7	3	5	3.20	0.56	0.043
Availability of credit facility	1/7	1	1/5	1/3	0.31	0.05	
Cost	1/3	5	1	3	1.49	0.26	
Ease of availability	1/5	3	1/3	1	0.66	0.11	

Table 10: Pair-wise comparison of sub-criteria to the reliability parameter

Criteria	Evenness	Strength	Count variation	Over twist	Geometric Mean (GM)	Normalised GM	Consistency Ratio (CR)
Evenness	1	3	5	7	3.20	0.56	0.043
Strength	1/3	1	3	5	1.49	0.26	
Count variation	1/5	1/3	1	3	0.66	0.11	
Over twist	1/7	1/5	1/3	1	0.31	0.05	

Table 11: Pair-wise comparison of sub-criteria to ease of availability parameter

Criteria	Ready availability	Waiting period	Troubles	Geometric Mean (GM)	Normalized GM	Consistency Ratio (CR)
Ready availability	1	5	7	3.26	0.73	0.056
Waiting period	1/5	1	3	0.84	0.18	
Troubles	1/7	1/3	1	0.36	0.08	

Table 12: Global weight of criteria and sub-criteria

Criteria	Nature	Relative weight	Criteria weight	Global weight
Evenness (E)	Beneficial	0.56	0.56	0.31
Strength (S)	Beneficial	0.26	0.56	0.14
Count variation (CV)	Cost	0.11	0.56	0.06
Over twist (OT)	Cost	0.05	0.56	0.03
Availability of credit facility (CF)	Beneficial	0.05	-	0.05
Cost (C)	Cost	0.26	-	0.26
Ready availability (RA)	Beneficial	0.73	0.11	0.08
Waiting period (WP)	Cost	0.18	0.11	0.02
Troubles/Hazards (T)	Cost	0.08	0.11	0.01

3.1 Application of AHP for Finding the Best Yarn Sourcing Point

The equation developed for calculating the value of the marketing chain (MI_{AHP}):

$$MI_{AHP} = \frac{E^{0.3179} S^{0.1485} CF^{0.055} RA^{0.0860}}{CV^{0.0664} OT^{0.031} C^{0.2634} WP^{0.0222} T^{0.0096}}$$

The survey analysis shows that the handloom weavers manufacture products using three major count groups of yarns. These are 90 - 110 Ne, 60 – 80 Ne and 20 – 40 Ne. The average price can be known against each alternative, and the values will be put in the equation.

For the other criteria, numerical values like 2,3 and 4 can be assigned based on the modal value against each criterion corresponding to each alternative, as observed from the responses in the survey. For example, for the criteria of evenness, yarns purchased from NHDC and directly from Burrabazar possess the best evenness, assigned by 4, followed by yarn purchased from the local market and Mahajan. It is a beneficial criterion where a higher value is desirable. Yarn purchased from NHDC shows less variation in the count, followed by yarn purchased from Burrabazar. Therefore, the criteria values are assigned by 2 and 3, respectively. Count variation in the yarn purchased from the local market and Mahajan shows more significant and almost the same count variation. Therefore, its value is assigned by 4. Since its lower value is desirable, it is a cost criterion. The same justification is applied to other criteria.

The cost value of yarns is also denoted by 2,3, and 4, and yarn prices are ascending to calculate the value of MI_{AHP} . Table 13 depicts alternative scores, global weights and rankings through MI_{AHP} values.

Table 13: Alternative score, global weight and ranking

Sourcing points	E	S	CV	OT	CF	C	RA	WP	T	MI _{AHP}	Rank
NHDC	3	4	3	5	5	5	1	4	5	1.05	4
Direct purchase from Barrabazar	3	4	3	5	5	2	1	3	5	1.34	2
Purchase through the local market	5	5	5	5	5	2	1	5	5	1.56	1
From Mahajan/Agent	2	3	2	5	5	5	1	5	5	0.90	5
Khadi Society	2	3	3	5	5	2	1	5	5	1.12	3

According to the MAHP model, as shown in Table 13, the most appropriate yarn-sourcing point was purchasing from the local market while considering the most critical and determining but conflicting parameters. This choice was influenced by cost, quality, lead time, and ease of purchase. Reducing transportation costs and ensuring a faster turnaround time for production can be possible by purchasing yarn from the local market, which also allows for closely monitoring the quality of the yarn and making any necessary adjustments or replacements as soon as possible.

3.2 Sensitivity Analysis

As a sensitivity analysis aimed to determine each factor's effect on the MCDM outputs independently, each criterion's weight was modified individually by 10% (minor change), 20% (medium change), or 30% (significant change) by raising it. The remaining criterion weights remained constant. Specific values of relative sensitivity coefficients obtained indicate several changes in alternative ranking owing to criterion weight modification (10 to 30% increase). Three criteria have been selected for the present research work: evenness, count variation, and cost. The change (Increase) of importance (weightage) in each criterion is considered to be 10%, 20%, and 30%. The revised ranking in the MI_{AHP} method is discussed hereunder.

3.2.1 The Most Suitable Option by Increasing the Importance of One of the Criteria

Table 14 shows the revised global weight of nine influencing elements after increasing the weightage of evenness by 10%, 20% & 30%.

Table 14: Revised Global weight

Criteria	Nature	Global Weight			
		MAHP Basic	Evenness		
			+ 10%	+20%	+30%
Evenness (E)	Beneficial	0.31	0.34	0.38	0.41
Strength (S)	Beneficial	0.12	0.14	0.13	0.12
Count Variation (CV)	Cost	0.05	0.06	0.06	0.05
Over Twist (OT)	Cost	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.02
Availability of Credit Facility (CF)	Beneficial	0.04	0.05	0.04	0.04
Cost (C)	Cost	0.22	0.25	0.23	0.22
Ready Availability (RA)	Beneficial	0.07	0.08	0.07	0.07

Waiting Period (WP)	Cost	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02
Troubles / Hazards (T)	Cost	0.008	0.009	0.008	0.008

Table 15 – 17 depicts the increasing weightage of evenness by 10%, 20%, and 30%, and finds the ranking through the MAHP method.

Table 15: Revised ranking for the change in global weight (10% increase in weightage of evenness)

Sourcing points	Mode value of nine elements on a scale of 1-5									MI _{AHP} value	Rank
	E	S	CV	OT	CF	C	RA	WP	T		
NHDC	3	4	3	5	5	5	1	4	5	1.10	4
Direct purchase from Burrabazar	3	4	3	5	5	2	1	3	5	1.39	2
Purchase through the local market	5	5	5	5	5	2	1	5	5	1.65	1
From Mahajan/ Agent	2	3	2	5	5	5	1	5	5	0.93	5
Khadi society	2	3	3	5	5	2	1	5	5	1.15	3

Table 16: Revised ranking for the change in global weight (20% increase in weightage of evenness)

Sourcing points	Mode value of nine elements on a scale of 1-5									MI _{AHP} value	Rank
	E	S	CV	OT	CF	C	RA	WP	T		
NHDC	3	4	3	5	5	5	1	4	5	1.10	4
Direct purchase from Burrabazar	3	4	3	5	5	2	1	3	5	1.41	2
Purchase through the local market	5	5	5	5	5	2	1	5	5	1.72	1
From Mahajan/ Agent	2	3	2	5	5	5	1	5	5	1.08	5
Khadi society	2	3	3	5	5	2	1	5	5	1.13	3

Table 17: Revised ranking for the change in global weight (30% increase in weightage of evenness)

Sourcing points	Mode value of nine elements on a scale of 1-5									MI _{AHP} value	Rank
	E	S	CV	OT	CF	C	RA	WP	T		
NHDC	3	4	3	5	5	5	1	4	5	1.22	3
Direct purchase from Burrabazar	3	4	3	5	5	2	1	3	5	1.54	2
Purchase through the local market	5	5	5	5	5	2	1	5	5	1.84	1
From Mahajan/ Agent	2	3	2	5	5	5	1	5	5	1.01	5
Khadi society	2	3	3	5	5	2	1	5	5	1.21	4

Figure 2: Rank in the MCDM method based on the MI_{AHP} value, considering the additional importance of evenness of the yarn

Table 18 shows the revised global weight of nine influencing elements after increasing the weightage of count variation by 10%, 20% & 30%.

Table 18: Revised Global weight

Criteria	Nature	Global Weight			
		MAHP Basic	Count Variation		
			+ 10%	+20%	+30%
Evenness (E)	Beneficial	0.31	0.34	0.37	0.40
Strength (S)	Beneficial	0.14	0.14	0.13	0.12
Count Variation (CV)	Cost	0.06	0.06	0.07	0.07
Over Twist (OT)	Cost	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.02
Availability of Credit Facility (CF)	Beneficial	0.05	0.05	0.04	0.04
Cost (C)	Cost	0.26	0.24	0.23	0.22
Ready Availability (RA)	Beneficial	0.08	0.08	0.07	0.07
Waiting Period (WP)	Cost	0.02	0.02	0.019	0.018
Troubles / Hazards (T)	Cost	0.0095	0.0090	0.0085	0.0081

Table 19 – 21 depict the increasing weightage of count variation by 10%, 20%, and 30% and finding the ranking through the MAHP method.

Table 19: Revised ranking for the change in global weight (10% increase in weightage of count variation)

Sourcing points	Mode value of nine elements on a scale of 1-5									MI _{AHP} value	Rank
	E	S	CV	OT	CF	C	RA	WP	T		
NHDC	3	4	3	5	5	5	1	4	5	1.09	4
Direct purchase from Burrabazar	3	4	3	5	5	2	1	3	5	1.38	2
Purchase through the local market	5	5	5	5	5	2	1	5	5	1.63	1
From Mahajan/ Agent	2	3	2	5	5	5	1	5	5	0.93	5
Khadi society	2	3	3	5	5	2	1	5	5	1.14	3

Table 20: Revised ranking for the change in global weight (20% increase in weightage of count variation)

Sourcing points	Mode value of nine elements on a scale of 1-5									MI _{AHP} value	Rank
	E	S	CV	OT	CF	C	RA	WP	T		
NHDC	3	4	3	5	5	5	1	4	5	1.14	3
Direct purchase from Burrabazar	3	4	3	5	5	2	1	3	5	1.42	2
Purchase through the local market	5	5	5	5	5	2	1	5	5	1.69	1
From Mahajan/ Agent	2	3	2	5	5	5	1	5	5	0.96	5
Khadi society	2	3	3	5	5	2	1	5	5	1.16	4

Table 21: Revised ranking for the change in global weight (30% increase in weightage of count variation)

Sourcing points	Mode value of nine elements on a scale of 1-5									MI _{AHP} value	Rank
	E	S	CV	OT	CF	C	RA	WP	T		
NHDC	3	4	3	5	5	5	1	4	5	1.18	3
Direct purchase from Burrabazar	3	4	3	5	5	2	1	3	5	1.46	2
Purchase through the local market	5	5	5	5	5	2	1	5	5	1.76	1
From Mahajan/ Agent	2	3	2	5	5	5	1	5	5	0.99	5
Khadi society	2	3	3	5	5	2	1	5	5	1.18	4

Figure 3: Rank in the MCDM method based on the MI_{AHP} value, considering the additional importance of the count variation of the yarn

Table 22 shows the revised global weight of nine influencing elements after increasing the weightage of cost by 10%, 20% & 30%.

Table 22: Revised Global weight

Criteria	Nature	Global Weight			
		MAHP Basic	Cost		
			+ 10%	+20%	+30%
Evenness (E)	Beneficial	0.31	0.30	0.29	0.28
Strength (S)	Beneficial	0.14	0.14	0.13	0.13
Count Variation (CV)	Cost	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.05
Over Twist (OT)	Cost	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.02
Availability of Credit Facility (CF)	Beneficial	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.04
Cost (C)	Cost	0.26	0.28	0.31	0.34
Ready Availability (RA)	Beneficial	0.08	0.08	0.07	0.07
Waiting Period (WP)	Cost	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.01
Troubles / Hazards (T)	Cost	0.009	0.009	0.008	0.008

Table 23 – 25 depicts the increasing weightage of cost by 10%, 20% and 30% and finding the ranking through the MAHP method.

Table 23: Revised ranking for the change in global weight (10% increase in weightage of cost)

Sourcing points	Mode value of nine elements on a scale of 1-5									MI _{AHP} value	Rank
	E	S	CV	OT	CF	C	RA	WP	T		
NHDC	3	4	3	5	5	5	1	4	5	0.99	4
Direct purchase from Burrabazar	3	4	3	5	5	2	1	3	5	1.30	2
Purchase through the local market	5	5	5	5	5	2	1	5	5	1.50	1
From Mahajan/ Agent	2	3	2	5	5	5	1	5	5	0.85	5
Khadi society	2	3	3	5	5	2	1	5	5	1.09	3

Table 24: Revised ranking for the change in global weight (20% increase in weightage of cost)

Sourcing points	Mode value of nine elements on a scale of 1-5									MI _{AHP} value	Rank
	E	S	CV	OT	CF	C	RA	WP	T		
NHDC	3	4	3	5	5	5	1	4	5	0.93	4
Direct purchase from Burrabazar	3	4	3	5	5	2	1	3	5	1.25	2
Purchase through the local market	5	5	5	5	5	2	1	5	5	1.44	1
From Mahajan/ Agent	2	3	2	5	5	5	1	5	5	0.81	5
Khadi society	2	3	3	5	5	2	1	5	5	1.06	3

Table 25: Revised ranking for the change in global weight (30% increase in weightage of cost)

Sourcing points	Mode value of nine elements on a scale of 1-5									MI _{AHP} value	Rank
	E	S	CV	OT	CF	C	RA	WP	T		
NHDC	3	4	3	5	5	5	1	4	5	0.88	4
Direct purchase from Burrabazar	3	4	3	5	5	2	1	3	5	1.21	2
Purchase through the local market	5	5	5	5	5	2	1	5	5	1.38	1
From Mahajan/ Agent	2	3	2	5	5	5	1	5	5	0.77	5
Khadi society	2	3	3	5	5	2	1	5	5	1.03	3

Figure 4: Rank in the MCDM method based on the MI_{AHP} value, considering the additional importance of the cost of the yarn

This sensitivity analysis provides some intriguing results.

Using the AHP methods to rank the options, considering the standard relative value of all the factors, it is noticed that purchasing yarn from the local market is the best option for weavers. This suggests that the weavers' demands and preferences, identified by AHP, are met when the yarn is sourced from the local market. It also implies that alternate ways of acquiring raw materials might be less beneficial for satisfying the assessed criteria. The AHP technique yields the same results as sensitivity analysis when factors like cost, evenness, and count variation (yarn quality) increase in significance up to 30% (10%, 20%, and 30%). So, the best and most efficient alternative would be to buy the raw material locally. Moreover, the sensitivity analysis shows that the AHP technique continues to rank local acquisition of raw materials as the most suitable and effective alternative, even when the importance of evenness, count variation, and cost is increased by up to 30%. Assessing procurement techniques demonstrates the consistency and reliability of the AHP approach.

The sensitivity analysis also shows that the AHP methods rank evenness the same regardless of the percentage increase (10%, 20%, and 30%). So, the best and most efficient alternative would be to buy the raw material locally. The sensitivity study shows that the AHP techniques continue to rank local raw material purchasing as the best alternative, even when the importance of evenness is increased by 10%, 20%, and 30%. This further demonstrates that the AHP technique is consistent and resilient when assessing procurement strategies, even when there are differences in important weights. Every business has unique procurement needs and priorities, and choosing the right evaluation approach requires careful consideration of these factors. The local market seems like the most obvious choice among the current yarn supply chains (buying yarn) because of the market's proximity, adaptability, and ease of management. Suppliers in the area may also be able to meet the organisation's unique demands and preferences more cheaply and precisely.

4 Conclusion

One area of focus could be creating a long-term supply chain that ensures proper supply of raw materials, i.e., yarn, to increase production efficiency and lower costs. Adopting an appropriate supply chain in the West Bengal handloom sector has been a source of contention for many years. One possible solution would be to create a centralised location for sourcing raw materials and distributing finished goods, expediting manufacturing and cutting transportation expenses.

The lack of an efficient supply chain model that ensures the timely delivery of raw materials and completed goods is one of the most significant issues the handloom sector faces. Despite various schemes provided by governmental and non-governmental organisations to solve these issues, there is always a need for constant improvement and innovation.

In the handloom industry, weavers are manufacturing various products, starting from *Gamcha* (local version of cheap Towel – thinner fabric), *Lungi* (wrap-around long for male casual wear) or daily use *sari* (ladies ethnic wear – basic – unstitched), *Dhoti* (mainly white fabric with embroidery at the bottom – male ethnic wear) to high-value Baluchari Sari, pure silk printed or embroidery. The raw materials supply chain for each product varies based on the product type. Procuring raw materials (yarn) involves a trade-off between quality, service, and price. For common handloom materials such as Gamcha, Lungi, or Ordinary Tant Sari, the raw material price (mostly yarn or thread) should be the cheapest to determine the optimum solution or pick the most suitable raw material choice in the global weight formula of MCDM analysis. However, by seeking low-cost materials while disregarding other yarn characteristics, such as quality factors such as yarn evenness, strength, count variation, or over-twist, weavers may eventually lose weaving efficiency and create low-grade defective goods with little market value.

AHP models assist in systematically studying raw material possibilities accessible to handloom weavers. They know the benefits and drawbacks of the yarn obtained from accessible sources such as NHDC, Local Market, Burrabazar (Kolkata wholesale market), Mahajan (Master weaver), and Khadi society, based on their experience as users. In most situations, we have discovered that purchasing from the local market is the best option, despite the higher raw material pricing than purchasing from NHDC, Master Weavers (Mahajan), Khadi Society, or Burrabazar.

The MCDM approach suggests the local market is the optimal sourcing option, but it is more costly. Establishing a platform for direct yarn manufacturers in handloom centres could enhance local sourcing, resilience, and competitiveness.

Conflict of interest

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